

Batak Traditional Religions

also known as "Parhudamadam", "Pemena", "Ugamo Malim", "Batak Hinduism", "Parmalim", "Ugamo Bangso Batak"

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Entry tags: Indic Religious Traditions, Religious Group, Syncretic Religions, Shamanism, Southeast Asian Religions

This entry covers practitioners of the Batak Traditional Religion, a system of practices that has been typically referred to as a traditional belief (aliran kepercayaan) by the Indonesian government as opposed to a formally recognized religion (agama). However, the Batak traditional religion has gone through various local iterations, focused on the worship of royalty as god, millenarianism, modern reforms, and a re-application of an appeal toward traditional cultural understandings. The traditional Batak religion is also often described as a form of Hinduism that is heavily localized, specific to the ethnic context of the Batak people, or Batak Hinduism.

Date Range: 1600 CE - 2020 CE

Region: North Sumatra

Region tags: Asia, Southeast Asia, Indonesia, Sumatra, North Sumatra

North Sumatra (Sumatra Utara) is an Indonesian province on the island of Sumatra. At the center of the province is Lake Toba, which was formed after the explosion of a supervolcano some 69 - 77,000 years ago. The region is considered the home of several Batak indigenous groups: Karo, Pakpak, Simalungun, Toba, Angkola, and Mandailing. Three of these groups: Karo, Toba, and Simalungun; but most especially communities of the Toba Batak, are associated with Batak traditional religions and Batak Hinduism.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Hirosue, Masashi. 1994. The Batak Millenarian Response to the Colonial Order, *Journal of Southeast Asian Studies*, 25 (2): 347 - 353.
- Source 2: Vergouwen, J.C. 1933 [1964]. The Social Organization and Customary Law of the Toba-Batak of Norther Sumatra [Het Rechtsleven der Toba-Bataks]. The Hague: Martinus Nijhoff.
- Source 3: Lamahu, Arafat Iskandar. 2020. "Ugamo Malim" Dalam Diskursus Keagamaan di Hutatinggi Kabupaten Toba Samosir. *Jurnal Sosiologi Agama: Jurnal Ilmiah Sosiologi Agama dan Perubahan Sosial*, 14 (1): 67 - 92.

- Source 1: Gultom, Ibrahim. 2010. Agama Malim di Tanah Batak. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara
- Source 2: Hirosue, Masashi. 1988. Prophets And Followers In Batak Millenarian Responses To The Colonial Order: Parmalim, Nasiakbagi And Parhudamdand, 1890- 1930. PhD Thesis. (Canberra: The Australian National University)
- Source 3: Kozok, Uli. 2009. Surat Batak;Sejarah Perkembangan Tulisan Batak (Berikut Pedoman Menulis Aksara Batak dan Cap Si Singamangaraja XII). Jakarta: KPG Gramedia.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.metmuseum.org/search-results#!/search?q=batak>
- Source 1 Description: Art Objects Related to the Batak People at the Metropolitan Museum of Art (The MET) in New York City

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://blogs.bl.uk/asian-and-african/2016/11/batak-manuscripts-in-the-british-library.html>
- Source 1 Description: Batak Manuscripts in the British Library
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.soas.ac.uk/news/newsitem132951.html>
- Source 2 Description: SOAS Digitizes North Sumatran 'Magic Book'

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: In the early-modern period some contestation emerged between upland Batak and lowland Muslim communities. During the colonial period, contestation was compounded by missionary efforts, which specifically aimed to convert non-Muslim uplanders. There have also been contestations over land-use rights.

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Batak traditions seem to have developed syncretism as a strategy of pluralism. Additionally, from independence onward, the Indonesian state has also developed its own notions of pluralism. For some time, this contestation differentiated between "religion" (agama) and "traditional beliefs" (aliran kepercayaan). However, a 2017 Supreme Court decision could allow Batak traditional religion to gain recognition as "believers of the faith" (penghaya kepercayaan).

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: Most common cultural contact with surrounding Malay Muslim populations has either been neutral or a feature of upstream-downstream relations, historically.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: There was substantial violence in this region during the colonial period, WWII, and during the Indonesian Genocide (1965 - 66). The 25th division of the Dai Nippon Teikoku Rikugun (Imperial Japanese Army) incorporated Medan and Sumatra as part of the Western Zone in March of 1942. When the Japanese left in 1945, Toba and Simalungun Batak fought each other as well as Javanese emigres and Achenese with abandoned Dutch or Japanese weapons. Several Batak leaders were also involved with gangster violence and military purges up through the Indonesian Genocide.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Again, when the Japanese left in 1945, Toba and Simalungun Batak fought each other as well as Javanese emigres and Achenese with abandoned Dutch or Japanese weapons. Several Batak leaders were also involved with gangster violence and military purges up through the Indonesian Genocide.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Individuals may convert out of the religion. Additionally, individuals may in-effect, convert into this religious group via marriage, although evidence of the latter appears to be scant.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

Notes: Except in instances where marriage into the group is involved. However, the main ritual, in those cases, would be marriage.

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: In the context of the 1940s a revivalist "Golongan Siradjabatak" (GS) movement called for "returns" to "traditional Batak" practices and to unify the religion of "all Batak." They recruited individuals from Batak Christian communities to return to Batak traditional religion.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1940 CE - 1970 CE

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: However, there is some indication that the 2017 decision recognizing several aliran kepercayaan (traditional beliefs) groups on Indonesian issued ID cards could lead to greater state

support in the future.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 350000

Notes: This is an estimate. It represents a conservative interpretation of census and colonial records. The total population could have been much greater, however, such as up to a million. Census records suggest there were 300,000 Christian Batak, 345,400 Muslim Batak, and the majority of the population being "Batak Heathens." However, we can rely on JC Vergouwen's "Het Rechleven der Toba-Bataks" (1933) to show that these "heathens" in the Dutch colonialist view, where most likely adherents to Batak traditional religions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1930 CE - 1939 CE

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 33

Notes: This is a minimum estimate for the date range based on census records, which have much more precise counts of Christian and Muslim Batak communities. It could be, however, a much greater number, such as 66%. The imprecise and qualitative wording of accounts makes it difficult to get a clear picture on just how big the traditional Batak religious community has been historically.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1930 CE - 1939 CE

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Batak manuscripts are called "pustaha," a term that seems to come from the Sanskrit "pustaka" meaning "book." They are composed by "datu" which are priests in Batak

society. These data are the rough equivalent of Brahmins within the Batak class-system.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

Notes: There is not a common set of stories that are associated with origins of the Batak script per se. Most scholars and sources record origins in the Old Kawi script of the Javanese court, especially located in the Empire of Majapahit. The Javanese court literature written in Kawi is best known for the kakawin genre. Within the kakawin genre, manuscripts such as the Arjunawiwaha were derived from importations of sections of the Mahabharata, from the 11th to 15th century. There are also local proto-Batak script inscriptions, such as Sitopayan I & II, which date to the 13th century. These indicate local origins for the Batak script, while illustrating connections to other early Island Southeast Asian scripts, such as Old Kawi. According to local oral histories, there was once a manuscript, the Tumbaga Holing, that it possessed all the knowledge of humanity. However, this manuscript is believed to have been stolen by the Dutch and spirited-away to what is now The Netherlands.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 25

Notes: Scholars could debate the interpretation here. However, the traditional Batak house (rumah, or rumah bolon) is itself a form of religious monumental architecture. There are certainly practical reasons for the constructions having large roofs and constructions that are based on the necessities of living in a tropical climate; i.e.: large gentle sloping roofs, with houses that are on platforms or stilts. However, the traditional houses often have ornamental features that make them clearly also religious structures, such as second stories, akin to temples, that are clearly predominantly decorative or ceremonial. The communal spaces are also ceremonial inside the structures. However, most settlements have had an ever decreasing number of these types of houses, especially from about the 1960s through the present. The estimate is that traditional houses make up 25% or less of structures by the 1970s onward.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Average size is 35 square meters.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The base of the average traditional house is 35m squared.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The average traditional house is 1.75m off the ground by terms of height. However, this is not the roof height, just the height of the stilts. 1.75m represents the distance from the earth to the floor of the traditional house.

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The largest Batak populated settlements at present may have few to zero traditional houses. In the historical past, during the early modern period, they would have been 100% traditional constructions.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– No

Notes: Not precisely. The traditional house itself, or communal houses in general, represent temples, in a sense.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, with sacrificial pillars.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: There is specifically a blending of some of these categories.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The key concept for the Batak is an essence called "tondi" or "tendi" depending on the dialect. This "tondi" has been translated as "soul-stuff," although in keeping with both South and Island Southeast Asian contexts, multiple conceptions of the soul are common. "Tondi" is associated with prowess and "living-soul-stuff" while the "death soul" (begu) can be set free when tondi leaves the body with death. The tondi-begu distinction implies a body/life-soul/death-soul distinction.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: There is a vast literature on soul-stuff (tondi, tendi) within Batak traditional religions, including records related to consumption of specific body parts in the historical past to acquire the tondi/tendi of another individual; but also there are debates about how many tondi/tendi a person has (sometimes up to seven) and some records suggest conceptions of tondi/tendi that are not specific to connections with physical body parts.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:
 - Yes
- ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:
 - Yes
- ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:
 - Yes
- ↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
 - Yes [specify]: Specifically a "spirit realm" suggested in some descriptions.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: The broad conception of tondi and the number of living beings that have tondi suggests that there is reincarnation in a number of possible forms, although the field is not clear on whether or not reincarnation is always present; i.e.: whether or not it is a universal phenomenon for all beings.

- ↳ In a human form:
 - Yes

- ↳ In animal/plant form:
 - No

Notes: Although there is not a sense that humans are directly reincarnated into rocks or trees, for example, there are spirits for rocks or trees - suggesting that there are other beings that experience forms of reincarnation that humans may not.

- ↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):
 - No

Notes: Again, there are rock-spirits - which would classify as inanimate objects and imply that there are some beings that can be reincarnated as rock-spirits - however, there are no common records of humans being reincarnated as inanimate objects.

- ↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):
 - No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: Yes, ton̄di (alt.: tendi) itself is understood to be a life-transcending causality although it is also - broadly - "life essence" or "soul stuff" in itself. Yet, ton̄di is also a "soul stuff" that an individual can lose - as a result of black magic or other supernatural phenomenon - and a person might well perish without. That said, the destiny of an individual is chosen by the ton̄di/tendi essence prior to birth, in communication with the high god.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism:

– Yes

Notes: Ritual cannibalism seems to end during the colonial period.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1900 CE

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Yes

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: Elaborate coffins

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– Yes

↳ Out-group humans are sacrificed:

– No

↳ In-group humans are sacrificed:

– Yes

Notes: Voluntary human sacrifice is mentioned in the historical past; including an account of priests travelling through villages and asking "who is tired" before the individuals to be sacrificed answer "I am." They would then be sacrificed regardless of class status.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1930 CE

↳ Other humans are sacrificed:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Manuscripts, which may be symbolically burned in some accounts.

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Burial houses could be argued to represent a "grave good" in and of themselves.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The Parhudamadam revival of the Batak religion saw Si Singamangaraja as a type of human-deity-incarnate on earth. This occurred after the death of the Si Singamangaraja in 1907.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1907 CE - 1950 CE

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god is most commonly referred to as Mula Djadi na Bolon. The supreme high god also changes in various historical epochs, by terms of popularity. Debata Asi Asi represents a form of a Trimurti - with Batara Guru (a common Island Southeast Asian epithet of Shiva), Mangalabolon, and Soripada. In more recent reforms, Soripada has been interpreted as a variant of Sripathi and Vishnu, although these links are not strongly evidenced in historical sources from the 20th century.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: However, there is an important god of the Earth and the underworld known as Boraspati ni Tano. Furthermore, in the creation story of the Batak, there is another naga-underworld serpent known as Naga Padoha. Scholars have argued that Boraspati is derived from Bṛhaspati, a Hindu god - Jupiter - that can be found in the Rigveda. That said, the evidence linking the two concepts beyond the name is not particularly convincing. The presence of a water deity Boru Saniang Naga - a female water-naga-serpent, indicates another possibility. Perhaps the epithet "Boru" "sa" was adopted into Batak, where "niang" is a common term that could be a feminization (similar to Thai "nang" or Balinese "njai" - a quite common term across Southeast Asia, meaning "lady") - and "naga" was added from Sanskrit, as it was elsewhere in Southeast Asia. Indeed, female naga-serpents are common across the region and commonly associated with under-realms/water-realms. In the case of the Batak, it is notable that Boraspati ni Tano is a male deity of the underworld that can cause drought and good harvest, while Naga Padoha is female and can cause earthquakes. Boru Saniang Naga is also female and can cause damage to communities by dragging sailors to their death under the waves.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– Yes

Notes: During the time of the Parmalim, the supreme-high-god was fused with the Si Singamagaradja. This process ended with the death of the last Si Singamagaradja in 1907 CE.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– Yes

Notes: In the context of those who view the lineage of the Si Singamagaradja as a clear lineage (marga) and the ancestor of all modern marga (lineages) there is the understanding that this individual is related to all elites. However, this does not mean that all lineages have seen the Si Singamagaradja as the supreme high-god (as opposed to Muladjadinabolon or Debata Asi Asi). There is debate about how the notion of Batak marga (lineages) relate to the Sanskrit concept of "paths" (marga) with the understanding that the term marga may have been adopted via the Javanese court of Majapahit.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: Specifically connected to Si Baso (priest-shamans) in later forms of the Batak traditional religion.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1907 CE - 2020 CE

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1907 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: Knowledge of the cosmos, spirit world, and tondi/tendi, all of which are connected and seen as part of this world, in a sense.
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: During the time of the Parmalim, the supreme-high-god was fused with the Si Singamagaradja.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: During the time of the Parmalim, the supreme-high-god was fused with the Si Singamagaradja.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: This depends very much on interpretation and time period.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: This depends very much on interpretation and time period. But several other gods are broadly referenced in the existing literature and historical records.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Specifically has lineage.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: During the time of the Parmalim, the supreme-high-god was fused with the Si Singamagaradja.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: More common among Si Baso.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: For Si Baso.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The definition of religious specialists, however, is somewhat flexible depending on the period. A traditional healer or medium might be ruled to be a religious specialist specifically because a god is communicating with them.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1907 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Only through monarch

– Yes

Notes: During the time of the Parmalim, the supreme-high-god was fused with the Si Singamagaradja.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through causal effects on this world, such as natural disasters, or through blessings upon harvests.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Notes: In the case of guardian spirits, they protect the individual, or maybe close relatives.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Guardian spirits tend to be bound to areas nearby where their living antecessors are present.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes
Notes: But this knowledge may have been restricted.

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
– Yes [specify]: Specifically related to pending danger and protection in the case of guardian spirits.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can reward:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
– Yes
Notes: With those spirits that communicate with antecessors through a medium, this is possible.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
– Yes
Notes: With those spirits that communicate with antecessors through a medium, this is possible.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes
Notes: With those spirits that communicate with antecessors through a medium, this is possible.

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Knowledge of danger/threats specifically, in the case of guardian spirits.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: With those spirits that communicate with antecessors through a medium, this is possible.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: Symbolic events or actions.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Batak religion has a host of supernatural beings that have knowledge of this world. They can be categorized into spirits of the natural world, presently and formerly human spirits, and spirit-gods. However, there are some divinities that transcend these categories, as does the principle essence of tondi (soul-stuff).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They have human-like emotions. For example, they can have a sense of betrayal.

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: For example: Boraspati ni Tano - a cosmic lizard - has the knowledge the world barren or bestow harvest blessings.
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They have specific powers that change based on the interpretation of the religion from the 19th through the 20th century.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1800 CE - 2000 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: During the time of the Si Singamangaradja, it would be possible to interpret the royalty as a mixed-human/divine being.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: During the time of the Si Singamangaradja, it would be possible to interpret the royalty as a mixed-human/divine being.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: During the time of the Si Singamangaradja, it would be possible to interpret the royalty as a mixed-human/divine being.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: But not always. The Si Singamangaradja does not seem to have predicted the end of its own lineage in 1907.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Royal responsibilities

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ In dreams:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: During the time of the Si Singamangaradja, it would be possible to interpret the royalty as a mixed-human/divine being. They ARE the monarch.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: By decree.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: The organization is dependent on whether or not we are speaking of a period when the group was technically trying to adhere to "monotheism" in which case "other beings" might be regulated to "prophet, saint & angel" status to conform with expectations of Christian and Muslim cosmologies.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Sexual taboos, as well as taboos of sacrifice.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes they find this pleasing!

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes they are in favor of this!

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Notes: Again, sometimes this is positive!

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– No

Notes: This does not seem to be a major concern; but could be interpreted as a concern by those syncretic practitioners who were influenced by Christianity from the 1940s through the 1970s, or so.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Coming of age rituals

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, if they are being directly lied to. Broad dishonesty can also result in punishment.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Notes: In the case of blood oaths, in particular.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings support sorcery, when appropriate.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: In some cases. Although, this may also be interpreted as a minor concern.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: During periods of the GS revival, this was absolutely the case.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1940 CE - 1970 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: However, interpretations vary.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Personal hygiene and ritual hygiene, broadly speaking, are the same concept.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Tondi/tendi (soul-stuff)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Specifically: natural disasters.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Done when angered!

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Especially in middle of the 20th century and later interpretations, punishments in the afterlife can be complex.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: Although in monotheistic interpretations, especially present during the decades when Batak Traditional religion leadership attempted to adhere to the pancasila policy's notions of monotheism, then yes, this was the case.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Blessings on antecessors.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Good harvests are extremely highly emphasized.
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - No
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Yes

Notes: Cosmic stability, lack of disasters.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: By the notion of ethical codes (adat). There is also a notion of an important "moral code" known as Dalihan Na Tolu, representing three key principles: showing respect to one's wife's family, showing respect to all women, and to care for one's close-relations.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: No, conventional, orthopraxic, and moral behavior are all bound by ethical codes (adat).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Although there may be restrictions for specific individuals within the society.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: At prescribed times and for prescribed members.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on

desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Broadly speaking, cattle has been explained as avoided as the Batak Traditional Religion is a form of "Hinduism" or "Batak Hindu Particularism," yet cattle were not a particularly common food resource and water buffalo are considered acceptable for consumption.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Voluntary sacrifice was historically practiced.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– Yes

Notes: Not explicitly self-sacrifice, but speaking up and saying "I am tired" was considered voluntary offering for sacrifice of humans.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Not per se. However, the notion that out-group members may not be married has occasionally been historically present. However, this notion is also tempered by the ability of individuals to change religious groups upon marriage.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The distance between individual household rituals is not regulated by time of day. These are calendrical rituals.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is not sufficient accounting of the size of these events to give an average. They can increase up to 100s of participants.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: These rituals are predominantly calendrical.

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: Tattoos as an adaptation of traditional artistic motifs are quite recent.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 2000 CE - 2020 CE

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– No

↳ Dress:

– Yes

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: There are two important classes of elites in Batak religious society. Yet, the society as a whole has not been rigorously organized into varnas; as much as some scholars have imagined. There are "datu" who read as similar to brahmakshatriya in historical epochs, up through 1907, at which point their role becomes purely symbolic, associated with keeping the pustaha texts, while also being magicians and diviners. The parbaringan are the priest-class. Although they are not keepers of texts; they conduct rituals. In the middle of the 20th century, shamans, known as "si baso" become more popular, although their popularity waned in the later quarter of the century. Slavery was historically practiced among Batak, although most enslaved peoples were war/raid captives from nearby peoples (Minangkabaus, Malays, so forth) or different Batak groups.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: The formal military was, however, conquered by Dutch colonialists in 1907.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1600 CE - 1907 CE

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The name of the Batak calendar is "Porhalaan." The names of the months are Batak, although the names of the days are Sanskrit. The term "hala" may derive from the Sanskrit "kala" for "time." Other elements may be either adopted from the Hindu calendar via the Javanese calendar. Alternatively they may just present as similarities.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: Cannibalism was also practiced but seems to have ended during the Dutch colonial period.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: There is also pastoralism evidenced in anthropological accounts and the historical record.

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